

THE BASICS OF LINGUODIDACTICS IN THE METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING FRENCH AT PRIMARY GRADES

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Abstract. *The given article discusses the essence and technological basis of teaching the French language to elementary school students based on linguistic didactic tools.*

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It is important to suggest that people have been interested in learning foreign languages since ancient times. According to I. V. Rakhmanov, a scientist who studied the history of learning foreign languages, even in ancient times they looked for and used the strangest and simplest ways to learn a foreign language. Methods and techniques have changed over the centuries, but the ideas put forward by Jan Kamensky, I. Pestolossi, A. Diesterweg are based on the fact that the process of learning a foreign language is complex and multicomponent. Based on this, the goal of teaching a child a foreign language is to teach him to communicate in this language. In order to be able to communicate in a foreign language, students need to have a certain level of vocabulary in this language. It is impossible to listen, understand or speak without acquiring the vocabulary of the language. Learning a foreign language at school from the primary grade is useful regardless of the child's abilities and capabilities, since a foreign language has a positive effect on the development of the child's cognitive processes - memory, attention, thinking, imagination and perception. A foreign language affects not only a child's ability to learn a language, but also to master their native language well.

According to B. Belyaev, "a foreign language teacher should know not only the subject, but also the child's psychophysiological characteristics." Having mastered a foreign language, a child's reflection of the world of objects can change. Mastering the vocabulary of a language broadens students' horizons, increases their knowledge of philology, history, culture and geography." A number of studies have been devoted to the role of the native language in mastering a foreign language.

According to Susan, D. Atkinson, S. Krashen, L. Prodromou, J. Kolker, J. Ustinova, the systematic use of the native language in studying a foreign language is the key to achieving the goal (based on the objectives of the lesson) and acquiring knowledge.

It is known that the words included in the vocabulary of a language are called lexicon. "Vocabulary" is a constantly developing element of language. According to the Sprachfllege magazine, a person knows four times more words than he uses. Knowledgeable adults know from 6,000 to 10,000 words in their native language. The vocabulary used by people in everyday life, conversations and messages is from 1,500 to 2,500 words in European languages. It can be concluded that even in their native language, people use a limited amount of vocabulary.

Certainly, the time spent on learning a language is strictly limited. In a secondary school setting, the vocabulary that students need to master must be understandable. Students must first learn the selected lexical units. This vocabulary in the methodology is called the lexical minimum.

The choice of the lexical minimum has a long history. The first ideas in this area were put forward by the teacher Ya.A. Kamensky. From the end of the 19th century to the beginning of the 20th century, a number of minimum vocabulary sets were created in connection with the idea that it is necessary to minimize the time spent on learning a foreign language and to give students the maximum necessary knowledge and skills.

While compiling a minimum vocabulary, the frequency of a word in context is taken as the main principle. Speaking about the scientific, theoretical and practical aspects of teaching a foreign language in the 1st grade, it can be suggested the following information regarding the French scientist S. Marcel (1793-1896), who was one of the first to put forward the idea that children already at the age of 6-7 have enough skills to learn a foreign language. He believed that it is important to develop children's speech activity.

One of Ch. Marcel's contemporaries, F. Gouin (1831-1896), concludes that children's speech activity can be developed through games, and says that a foreign language can be studied based on the following principles.

The material prepared for teaching a foreign language is first understood by ear, and then used in oral speech as practice.

Secondly, since a foreign language is saturated with emotions, oral speech activity should be organized not from words, but from sentences centered on verbs.

According to G. Sweet and V. Fietor, teaching children aged 6-7 a foreign language will have a positive effect on the development of 4 skills. For developing oral speech skills in children aged 10, it should be focused on the psychological and pedagogical aspects, the main mental functions of a first-grader (feeling, attention, memory, imagination, perception, etc.) should be paid attention also. In general, the listed functions form the basis for the assimilation of foreign language material by children.

It has been noted that a child aged 6-7 is interested in everything. It is important to develop the skills of analysis, comparison and generalization in children of this age. According to many psychological studies, comparison is one of the most effective methods for developing observation and perception. At the same time, errors are reduced and perception is developed.

In such conditions, a child learns to speak a foreign language faster and more successfully, if we take French as an example. There is an opinion that knowledge acquired in childhood is acquired forever. But if you do not pay attention to the development of oral speech activity in French (in general in foreign languages), the ability to speak orally will disappear.

While learning French, especially phonetics, it is very important how the teacher pronounces words and phrases with his face and voice. Undoubtedly, the teacher's voice should be soft and gentle, and the face - cheerful, happy or serious, depending on the tone of voice.

While learning French in the 1st grade, it is necessary to pay attention to the student's ability to communicate with other people, that is, the formation of language competence.

By summarising it should be suggested that the first-grade students should listen carefully to a dialogue between two students on a topic and observe whether they speak correctly and using the paired interactive method, it is necessary to practice the same dialogue with all students. French must be mastered as a means of communication. Students can use the words and phrases learned during the lesson and see their results.

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